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New data on the genus *Chionea* (Diptera, Limoniidae) of former Yugoslavia

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SUMMARY. With a few records from Montenegro, *Chionea alpina* Bezzi thus far was the only recorded species of the winter crane fly genus *Chionea* Dalman in former Yugoslavia. We confirm the presence of this species in Montenegro and record it for the first time from Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Chionea austriaca* (Christian) is a second species occurring in former Yugoslavia and is recorded here for the first time from Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia. Identifying characteristics of the species are given and illustrated with photos. The shortage of data on *Chionea* species in Southeast Europe is discussed.

KEY WORDS: Bosnia and Herzegovina, crane fly, identification, Montenegro, Serbia.

INTRODUCTION

Among the cold-adapted flies, the crane fly genus *Chionea* Dalman, 1816 is remarkable because of the peculiar biology and associated structural adaptations. Adults generally have a hidden, soil-inhabiting lifestyle, living in crevices, burrows, soil cavities and subnivean spaces. They can occasionally be encountered moving spider-like over snow covered surfaces, which gave rise to the vernacular name ‘snow flies’. Structural adaptations to their subterranean life style are the relatively short antennae, small eyes, short and robust body with a reduced thorax and a largely membranous abdomen, extremely reduced wings, and short and stout legs (Fig. 1). The species are cold-adapted, with adults being active at ambient temperatures between about 0 and –4 °C (Byers 1983).

Fig. 1. *Chionea alpina* male, Montenegro, Mt. Somina, Ćurilovac, Jama u Katunu pit. (Photo Siniša Ognjenović).

Usually, the number of *Chionea* specimens observed in the field is rather low, but occasionally they can occur in massive numbers. For instance, *C. alexandriana* Garrett, 1922, *C. jellisoni* Byers, 1983, *C. obtusa* Byers, 1983, and *C. valga* Harris, 1841 were irregularly collected in high numbers in North America (Byers 1983). In Europe incidental high population densities are recorded for *C. araneoides* Dalman, 1816, *C. austriaca* (Christian, 1980), *C. belgica* (Becker, 1912), *C. botoaneanvii* (Burghele-Balacesco, 1969), and *C. lutescens* Lundström, 1907 (Oosterbroek and Reusch 2008; Thomas 1890).

Of the 11 species of *Chionea* known to occur in Europe, thus far only *Chionea alpina* Bezzi, 1908, *C. araneoides* and *C. austriaca* have been reliably recorded in former Yugoslavia. *Chionea alpina* was recorded for Montenegro (Simova-Tošić 1992, as *C. lutescens*; Oosterbroek and Simova-Tošić 2004; Oosterbroek and Reusch 2008; Oosterbroek 2023), while *C. araneoides* and *C. austriaca* were reported from Slovenia (Franz 1989; Novak *et al.* 2007; Oosterbroek and Reusch 2008; Oosterbroek 2023). Krzeminski (1982) mapped *C. lutescens* for Bosnia and Herzegov-

ina, but according to Oosterbroek and Reusch (2008) this is to be confirmed and the record probably refers to *C. major* Strobl, 1900, a nomen dubium.

The number of species of *Chionea* generally always remains modest per area, with for instance six in northern Italy, five in Germany, four per country in France, Switzerland and Austria, and three in Sweden, Finland, the Czech Republic, Poland, and Romania (Oosterbroek 2023).

A first attempt to reconstruct the phylogeny and biogeographic history of the genus was published by De Jong and Cilberti (2014).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material discussed in this paper was intermittently collected from 1990 to 2023. The snow flies were exclusively collected in very cold caves and pits with ice and snow by hand and by long term vinegar traps baited with rotten meat. Two males of *C. austriaca* were found in mesovoid shallow substratum (MSS) traps on Mt. Stara planina, Dojkinci. The specimens are preserved in Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, the Netherlands.

Identification was performed with Oosterbroek and Reusch (2008), which covers all European *Chionia* species. Photos of the details of the bodies were made with a Zeiss Discovery V20 stereomicroscope and processed with Adobe Photoshop in Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

RESULTS

Chionea alpina Bezzi, 1908 Figs 1–5

Identification

Males of *C. alpina* can readily be identified by the presence of the paired, extremely long and coiled prolongations of the aedeagus, which is always clearly visible in ethanol preserved specimens (Fig. 2). Other character states occurring in this species are the relatively short, strong and widely spaced setae on the legs (Fig. 5), and the absence of a comb of setae on male sternite 9 (Fig. 3). The paramere of *C. alpina* has a well-developed lower corner, the upper corner bears a small apical hook (Fig. 4). Like the males, females of *C. alpina* can be distinguished by the short, strong and widely spaced setae on the legs (Fig. 5) (Oosterbroek and Reusch 2008).

Fig. 2. *Chionea alpina*. Male hypopygium, dorsal view (specimen from Montenegro, Durmitor Mt.).

Fig. 3. *Chionea alpina*. Male hypopygium, ventral view (specimen from Montenegro, Durmitor Mt.).

Fig. 4. *Chionea alpina*. Male parameres, left lateral view (specimen from Montenegro, Durmitor Mt.).

Fig. 5. *Chionea alpina*. Male left leg, femur and tibia (specimen from Montenegro, Durmitor Mt.).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

Bosnia and Herzegovina

3 males: planina Lebršnik Mt., jama Čavkanica pit, 9.09.2006, leg. S. Ognjenović.

Montenegro

2 males: Durmitor Mt., Sedlo, Zupci, pećina u Zupcima cave, 2100 m, 28.06.1990, leg. D. Pavićević;

5 males, 1 female: Durmitor Mt., Sedlo, Zupci, pećina u Zupcima cave, 31.07.1991, leg. D. Pavićević;

1 male: Durmitor Mt., Zeleni Vir, 2100 m, Zelenovirska pećina cave, 2.08.1991, leg. D. Pavićević;

1 female: Durmitor Mt., Zeleni vir, Zelenovorska pećina cave, 2100 m, 2.08.1994, leg. A. Milosavljević.;

5 males: Somina Mt., Ćurilovac, 1200 m, jama u Katunu pit, 8.08.2010, leg. S. Ognjenović;

1 male: Prokletije Mts, Maja Kolata, Katun Bjelić, jama Kolektor pit, 2052 m, 20.07.2014-28.07.2015, leg. M. Popović;

1 male, 1 female: Durmitor Mt., Obla Glava, Ledena pećina cave, 2160 m., 5.08.1992, leg. I. Karaman;

4 females: Prokletije Mts, Maja Kolata, Katun Bjelić, jama Dve sise pit, 2000 m., 20.07.2014-28.07.2015, leg. M. Popović.

Chionea austriaca (Christian, 1980) Figs 6–9

Identification

Males of *C. austriaca* can be distinguished by the relatively small diameter of the aedeagus and the shape of its tip, which bears a pair of short filaments (Fig. 8). The lower corner of the paramere is not as strong as the upper corner and the upper corner usually bears an appressed apical hook (Fig. 8). Male sternite 9 bears no medial comb of setae (Fig. 7). Setae on the legs are relatively long, slender and closely set (Fig. 9). Females of *C. austriaca* can only be identified by inference, with reference to the presence of thin setae on the legs (Fig. 9) and the association with males of the species (Oosterbroek and Reusch 2008).

MATERIAL EXAMINED

Bosnia and Herzegovina

1 female: Olovo, Bijambare, Bijambarska pećina cave, 9.11.2008, leg. I.M. Karaman. Serbia

1 male: Suva planina Mt., Mali Trem, jama Savina Propas pit, 1750 m, 8.06.2000–17.06.2001, leg. S. Ognjenović;

1 male, 2 females: Suva planina Mt., Ždrebica, 1400 m, Bezimena jama pit, 9.06.2000–17.06.2001, leg. S. Ognjenović;

1 male: Pester Plateau, Kačunova pećina cave, 1100 m, 17.10.2008, leg. S. Ognjenović;

2 males: Stara planina Mt., Dojkinci, Tupavica waterfall, 1050 m, MSS traps, 03.06.2021–04.06.2023, leg. D. Antić, M. Šević, D. Stojanović.

Fig. 6. *Chionea austriaca*. Male hypopygium, dorsal view (specimen from Serbia, Suva planina Mt.)

Fig. 7. *Chionea austriaca*. Male hypopygium, ventral view (specimen from Serbia, Suva planina Mt.).

Fig. 8. *Chionea austriaca*. Male parameres and aedeagus, left lateral view (specimen from Serbia, Suva planina Mt.).

Fig. 9. *Chionea austriaca*. Male left leg, femur and tibia (specimen from Serbia, Suva planina Mt.).

DISCUSSION

It is obvious that the genus *Chionea* has a very restricted presence in the Balkans, even if additional species might show up in the future. Simova-Tošić (1992) recorded *C. lutescens* for Montenegro, but testimonial material examined by Oosterbroek and Reusch (2008) all proved to belong to *C. alpina*. The nearest reliable records of *C. lutescens* to the Balkans are from Switzerland and Austria (Oosterbroek 2023).

Next to the countries of the former Yugoslavia, the Balkans also include Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, and European Turkey, but no additional *Chionea* records from this augmented area are currently available (Oosterbroek 2023).

Records of *C. alpina* for Slovenia by Simova-Tošić and Sivec (1977), Novak and Kustor (1983), Novak (2005), and Novak *et al.* (2007) could not be confirmed by Oosterbroek and Reusch (2008) or proved to concern *C. austriaca*. *Chionea alpina* is known to occur in the Pyrenees, the Alps and adjacent southeast France, Ba-

Fig. 10. Localities with *Chionea alpina* (red dots) and *Chionea austriaca* (yellow dots). AL: Albania; BG: Bulgaria; BiH: Bosnia and Herzegovina; MNE: Montenegro; SRB: Serbia.

varia in Germany, northern Italy and Romania. Its presence in Montenegro and Bosnia and Herzegovina, as demonstrated in this paper, makes the existence of *C. alpina* in geographically intermediate Slovenia nevertheless very plausible.

As the modest numbers of known *Chionea* species in other European countries suggest (see Introduction), these are probably not an artefact of under-collecting, but represent an actual biological phenomenon. According to the historical biogeographic analysis of De Jong and Ciliberti (2014), the genus probably had an opportunity to spread southwards in Europe during the Last Glacial Maximum (26.500–19.000 years ago). The niche models of De Jong and Ciliberti (2014) for that period and for the present show relatively low suitability for the occurrence of *Chionea* in the Balkans, with the more favourable areas lying in the western part of the region (figures 5C and D in De Jong and Ciliberti, 2014). It thus seems probable that the number of known *Chionea* species in the Balkans will not increase substantially, irrespective of the intensity of collecting activities.

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